

Justin Johnson's Neural Style Torch Implementation on Github Explained

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1 Introduction

Justin Johnson was kind enough to share his torch implementation [3] of the paper "A Neural Algorithm of Artistic Style" by Leon A. Gatys, Alexander S. Ecker, and Matthias Bethge [1, 2]. The primary goal of this paper is to explain Justin's implementation when it is not particularly clear.

2 Setting up the network

Listing 1 shows the code for setting up the network. During network setup, the Total Variation (TV) loss layer, the content layers, and the style layers are added to the VGG-19 network. The TV loss layer is the first layer added to the network. It has to be as we are going to need to compute the derivatives of the TV loss with respect to the generated image in the backward pass. Any content/style layer that we add directly follows the VGG-19 layer of the same name. Assuming the content and style layers are the default ones (relu4_2 for the content layer and relu1_1, relu2_1, relu3_1, relu4_1, and relu5_1 for the style layers), the network will look like what is depicted in Figure ???. It should be noted that in the Gatys paper, the default layers are conv4_2 for the content layer and conv1_1, conv2_1, conv3_1, conv4_1, and conv5_1 for the style layers. I do not think it makes much difference but it is worth mentioning it. It should also be noted that in the Gatys paper, there is no TV loss layer (regularization). Regularization in the form of a TV loss helps with high frequency noise in the generated image. If the content image is chosen as the initial image, I do not think regularization is needed to get good results. It is when you start with a random image that regularization is needed.

Note that we do not define a loss function for the network as the network is already trained. The loss functions are going to be defined in the individual content and style modules (layers) that were added to the original VGG-19 network.

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Listing 1: Code for setting up the network

```
-- Set up the network, inserting style and content loss modules
local content_losses, style_losses = {}, {}
local next_content_idx, next_style_idx = 1, 1
local net = nn.Sequential()
if params.tv_weight > 0 then
  local tv_mod = nn.TVLoss(params.tv_weight):type(dtype)
  net:add(tv_mod)
end
for i = 1, #cnn do
  if next_content_idx <= #content_layers or next_style_idx <= #style_layers then
    local layer = cnn:get(i)
    local name = layer.name
    local layer_type = torch.type(layer)
    local is_pooling = (layer_type == 'cudnn.SpatialMaxPooling' or
      layer_type == 'nn.SpatialMaxPooling')
    if is_pooling and params.pooling == 'avg' then
      assert(layer.padW == 0 and layer.padH == 0)
      local kW, kH = layer.kW, layer.kH
      local dW, dH = layer.dW, layer.dH
      local avg_pool_layer = nn.SpatialAveragePooling(kW, kH, dW, dH):type(dtype)
      local msg = 'Replacing max pooling at layer %d with average pooling'
      print(string.format(msg, i))
      net:add(avg_pool_layer)
    else
      net:add(layer)
    end
    if name == content_layers[next_content_idx] then
      print("Setting up content layer", i, ":", layer.name)
      local norm = params.normalize_gradients
      local loss_module = nn.ContentLoss(params.content_weight, norm):type(dtype)
      net:add(loss_module)
      table.insert(content_losses, loss_module)
      next_content_idx = next_content_idx + 1
    end
    if name == style_layers[next_style_idx] then
      print("Setting up style layer ", i, ":", layer.name)
      local norm = params.normalize_gradients
      local loss_module = nn.StyleLoss(params.style_weight, norm):type(dtype)
      net:add(loss_module)
      table.insert(style_losses, loss_module)
      next_style_idx = next_style_idx + 1
    end
  end
end
end
end
```


3 Running the optimizer

The optimizer relies on the function `feval` shown in listing 2 to get the loss and the derivatives of the loss with respect to the image that is being generated `x`. The image being generated is an rgb image, that is, each pixel of the image stores a red, green, and blue value that is supposed to be between 0 and 255 (or 0 to 1 after normalization). Computing the derivatives of the loss with respect to the image means computing the derivatives of the loss with respect to the three rgb values (aka the colors) of the pixels. When the optimizer gets the derivatives from `feval`, it updates the colors of the pixels according to those derivatives.

3.1 Forward propagation

What happens in listing 2 when

```
net:forward(x)
```

is called? The `updateOutput` method gets called for each module (layer) of the network going forward, that is, from left to right. We are only interested in the modules (layers) that we added to the original VGG-19 network. These added modules (layers) are pass-through (output is equal to the input), which means the added modules (layers) do not modify the outputs of the original VGG-19 modules (layers).

We are going to look at what happens when the neural network goes through a forward pass, in particular, in the `updateOutput` methods of the content, style, and TV loss modules (layers).

3.1.1 ContentLoss:updateOutput

The code for the `updateOutput` method of the content loss module (layer) is shown in listing 3.

In listing 3, `input` are the feature responses at the input of the content module (layer) which are also the feature responses at the output of the previous VGG-19 module (layer). The input is either the feature responses of the content image (when in capture mode) or the feature responses of the image that is being generated (when in loss mode).

Listing 2: Code for evaluating the loss and derivatives

```
-- Function to evaluate loss and gradient. We run the net forward and
-- backward to get the gradient, and sum up losses from the loss modules.
-- optim.lbfgs internally handles iteration and calls this function many
-- times, so we manually count the number of iterations to handle printing
-- and saving intermediate results.
local num_calls = 0
local function feval(x)
  num_calls = num_calls + 1
  net:forward(x)
  local grad = net:updateGradInput(x, dy)
  local loss = 0
  for _, mod in ipairs(content_losses) do
    loss = loss + mod.loss
  end
  for _, mod in ipairs(style_losses) do
    loss = loss + mod.loss
  end
  maybe_print(num_calls, loss)
  maybe_save(num_calls)

  collectgarbage()
  -- optim.lbfgs expects a vector for gradients
  return loss, grad:view(grad:nElement())
end
```

Listing 3: Code for updateOutput of the content loss

```
function ContentLoss:updateOutput(input)
  if self.mode == 'loss' then
    self.loss = self.crit:forward(input, self.target) * self.strength
  elseif self.mode == 'capture' then
    self.target:resizeAs(input):copy(input)
  end
  self.output = input
  return self.output
end
```

Listing 4: Code for capturing the content targets

```
-- Capture content targets
for i = 1, #content_losses do
    content_losses[i].mode = 'capture'
end
print 'Capturing content targets'
print(net)
content_image_caffe = content_image_caffe:type(dtype)
net:forward(content_image_caffe:type(dtype))
```

The mode is set to capture prior to starting the optimizer to store the feature responses of the content image at the input of the content module (layer) in `self.target`. In the Gatys paper, those feature responses are called P_{ij}^l . Capture happens when the code shown in listing 4 is called. This code is executed once as the content image never changes (unlike the image that is being generated).

When the optimizer is running, the mode is set to loss. The input are the feature responses of the image that is being generated. In the Gatys paper, those feature responses are called F_{ij}^l . In listing 3,

```
self.loss = self.crit:forward(input, self.target) * self.strength
```

where `self.crit = nn.MSECriterion()` computes the loss using the following formula (without considering the strength of the contribution for simplicity):

$$E_l = \frac{1}{N_l * M_l} \sum_{i,j} (F_{ij}^l - P_{ij}^l)^2$$

where N_l is the number of feature maps (C in the code) and M_l is the size of the feature maps (H times W in the code). This is equation (1) in the Gatys paper (within a constant factor).

3.1.2 StyleLoss:updateOutput

The code for the `updateOutput` method of the style loss module is shown in listing 5.

In listing 5, `input` are the feature responses at the input of the style module (layer) which are also the feature responses at the output of the previous VGG-19 module (layer). The input is either the feature responses of the style image (in capture mode) or the feature responses of the image that is being generated (in loss mode).

In listing 5,

```
self.G = self.gram:forward(input)
```

computes the Gram matrix for the input which can be either the feature responses of the style image or the feature responses of the image that is being generated. The forward method of the Gram module calls its `updateOutput` method.

The code for the `updateOutput` method of the Gram matrix module is shown in listing 6.

Listing 5: Code for updateOutput of the style loss

```
function StyleLoss:updateOutput(input)
  self.G = self.gram:forward(input)
  self.G:div(input:nElement())
  if self.mode == 'capture' then
    if self.blend_weight == nil then
      self.target:resizeAs(self.G):copy(self.G)
    elseif self.target:nElement() == 0 then
      self.target:resizeAs(self.G):copy(self.G):mul(self.blend_weight)
    else
      self.target:add(self.blend_weight, self.G)
    end
  elseif self.mode == 'loss' then
    self.loss = self.strength * self.crit:forward(self.G, self.target)
  end
  self.output = input
  return self.output
end
```

Listing 6: Code for updateOutput of the GramMatrix module

```
function Gram:updateOutput(input)
  assert(input:dim() == 3)
  local C, H, W = input:size(1), input:size(2), input:size(3)
  local x_flat = input:view(C, H * W)
  self.output:resize(C, C)
  self.output:mm(x_flat, x_flat:t())
  return self.output
end
```

Listing 7: Code for capturing the style targets

```

-- Capture style targets
for i = 1, #content_losses do
    content_losses[i].mode = 'none'
end
for i = 1, #style_images_caffe do
    print(string.format('Capturing style target %d', i))
    for j = 1, #style_losses do
        style_losses[j].mode = 'capture'
        style_losses[j].blend_weight = style_blend_weights[i]
    end
    net:forward(style_images_caffe[i]:type(dtype))
end

```

In the Gatys paper, the Gram matrix is defined as

$$G_{ij}^l = \sum_k F_{ik}^l F_{jk}^l$$

In matrix notation, it can be written as $G = FF^T$. Since F has N_l (C in the code) rows and M_l (product of H and W in the code) columns, G is a square matrix of size $N_l N_l$.

Going back to the `updateOutput` method of the style loss module (listing 5), the mode is set to capture prior to starting the optimizer in order to store the Gram matrix (in `self.target`) of the feature responses of the style image at the input of the content module (layer). In the Gatys paper, that Gram matrix is called A_{ij}^l . Capture happens when the code shown in listing 7 is called. It is called once as the style image never changes unlike the image that is being generated.

When the optimizer is running, the mode is set to loss. The input are the feature responses of the image that is being generated. In listing 5,

```
self.G = self.gram:forward(input)
```

computes the Gram matrix of the feature responses of the image that is being generated. In the Gatys paper, the Gram matrix is called G_{ij}^l .

```
self.loss = self.strength * self.crit:forward(self.G, self.target)
```

where `self.crit = nn.MSECriterion()` computes the loss using the following formula (without considering the strength of the contribution for simplicity):

$$E_l = \frac{1}{N_l * N_l} \sum_{i,j} (G_{ij}^l - A_{ij}^l)^2$$

where N_l is the number of feature maps (C in the code) and M_l is the size of the feature maps (product of H and W in the code). This is equation (4) in the Gatys paper within a constant factor.

Listing 8: Code for updateOutput of the TV loss

```
function TVLoss:updateOutput(input)
    self.output = input
    return self.output
end
```

Listing 9: Code for initializing the derivatives

```
-- Run it through the network once to get the proper size for the gradient
-- All the gradients will come from the extra loss modules, so we just pass
-- zeros into the top of the net on the backward pass.
local y = net:forward(img)
local dy = img.new(#y):zero()
```

3.1.3 TVLoss:updateOutput

The code for the updateOutput method of the Total Variation (TV) loss module is shown in listing 8. It actually does nothing, as expected, besides passing through (unchanged) the input to the output.

3.2 Backward propagation

What happens when

```
local grad = net:updateGradInput(x, dy)
```

in the feval function (listing 2) is called? In torch, when

```
gradInput = updateGradInput(input, gradOutput)
```

is called for a neural network (like here), the updateGradInput methods are called for each module of the neural network going backwards hence the term "backward propagation". Given a module (layer), **input** is the input to the module (layer), that is, the feature responses at the input or, if you prefer, the feature responses at the output of the previous module (layer). **gradOutput** are the derivatives (of the loss) with respect to the output of the module (feature responses at the output). **gradInput** are the derivatives (of the loss) with respect to the input of the module (feature responses at the input). As you go backwards in the neural network, the input of the current module (layer) becomes the output of the previous module (layer). As you go backwards and reach the first module (layer) of the network, **gradInput** are actually the derivatives (of the loss) with respect to the image being generated, which is exactly what the optimizer asks for. In listing 2, **x** represents the generated image, that is, the rgb values at the pixels and **dy** the derivatives with respect to the output. It should be noted that **dy** is initialized to zero when the code in listing 9 gets called.

Recall that

```
local grad = net:updateGradInput(x, dy)
```

in listing 2 will not work (compute the correct derivatives) unless

Listing 10: Code for updateGradInput of the content loss module

```
function ContentLoss:updateGradInput(input, gradOutput)
  if self.mode == 'loss' then
    if input:nElement() == self.target:nElement() then
      self.gradInput = self.crit:backward(input, self.target)
    end
    if self.normalize then
      self.gradInput:div(torch.norm(self.gradInput, 1) + 1e-8)
    end
    self.gradInput:mul(self.strength)
    self.gradInput:add(gradOutput)
  else
    self.gradInput:resizeAs(gradOutput):copy(gradOutput)
  end
  return self.gradInput
end
```

```
net:forward(x)
```

is called just prior. In other words, a backward method should only be executed after the corresponding forward method.

We are going to look at what happens when the neural network goes through a backward pass, in particular, in the updateGradInput methods of the content layers (`ContentLoss:updateGradInput`), style layers (`StyleLoss:updateGradInput`), and the TV loss layer (`TVLoss:updateGradInput`).

3.2.1 ContentLoss:updateGradInput

The code for the updateGradInput method of the content loss module is shown in listing 10.

Before the optimizer is launched, the mode is set to loss. This is the only mode we need to worry about here. In listing 10,

```
self.gradInput = self.crit:backward(input, self.target)
```

(which will always called by the way) computes the derivatives of the loss with respect to the input, that is, the feature responses of the generated image at the input of the module (layer). Recall that `self.target` stored the feature responses of the content image in the capture phase. This means that the loss is correctly computed between the feature responses of the generated image and the feature responses of the content image. In listing 10,

```
self.gradInput:add(gradOutput)
```

adds the derivatives of the loss with respect to the output to the derivatives of the loss with respect to the input in order to be able to propagate back the contributions of modules (layers) that were previously processed. Because this is a content loss module (layer), the input is the same as the output, so it makes total sense dimension-wise to add `gradOutput` to `self.gradInput`.

Listing 11: Code for updateGradInput of the style loss module

```
function StyleLoss:updateGradInput(input, gradOutput)
  if self.mode == 'loss' then
    local dG = self.crit:backward(self.G, self.target)
    dG:div(input:nElement())
    self.gradInput = self.gram:backward(input, dG)
    if self.normalize then
      self.gradInput:div(torch.norm(self.gradInput, 1) + 1e-8)
    end
    self.gradInput:mul(self.strength)
    self.gradInput:add(gradOutput)
  else
    self.gradInput = gradOutput
  end
  return self.gradInput
end
```

3.2.2 StyleLoss:updateGradInput

The code for the updateGradInput method of the style loss module is shown in listing 11.

Before the optimizer is launched, the mode is set to loss. This is the only mode we need to worry about here. In listing 11,

```
local dG = self.crit:backward(self.G, self.target)
```

computes the derivatives of the loss with respect to the Gram matrix of the feature responses of the generated image. Recall that `self.target` stored the Gram matrix of the feature responses of the style image during the capture phase. This means that the loss is correctly computed between the Gram matrix of the feature responses of the generated image and the Gram matrix of the feature responses of the style image. We can write

```
local dG = self.crit:backward(self.G, self.target)
```

in listing 11 in matrix form as

$$dG = \frac{\partial E}{\partial G}$$

where E is the style loss for the module (layer). It should really be E_l but we all know this refers to the current style module (layer).

In listing 11,

```
self.gradInput = self.gram:backward(input, dG)
```

invokes the updateGradInput of the Gram matrix module.

The code for the updateGradInput method of the Gram matrix module is shown in listing 12.

In listing 12, `input` are the feature responses of the generated image (F_{ij} in the Gatys paper or simply F in matrix form). `gradOutput` is `dG`, that is, the derivatives of the loss with respect to the Gram matrix. What we want `self.gradInput` to be is $\frac{\partial E}{\partial F}$, that is, the

Listing 12: Code for updateGradInput of the Gram matrix module

```
function Gram:updateGradInput(input, gradOutput)
  assert(input:dim() == 3 and input:size(1))
  local C, H, W = input:size(1), input:size(2), input:size(3)
  local x_flat = input:view(C, H * W)
  self.gradInput:resize(C, H * W):mm(gradOutput, x_flat)
  self.gradInput:addmm(gradOutput:t(), x_flat)
  self.gradInput = self.gradInput:view(C, H, W)
  return self.gradInput
end
```

derivatives of the loss with respect to the feature responses of the generated image (F_{ij} in the Gatys paper or simply F in matrix form). What is actually computed as `self.gradInput` in the code is

$$\text{self.gradInput} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial F} F + \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial G}\right)^T F$$

Let's see if this is equal to $\frac{\partial E}{\partial F}$. For that, we need to do a bit of work. The style loss is defined as

$$E = \sum_{m,n} (G_{mn} - A_{mn})^2$$

with

$$G_{mn} = \sum_k F_{mk} F_{nk}$$

We have

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial F_{ij}} = 2 \sum_{m,n} (G_{mn} - A_{mn}) \frac{\partial G_{mn}}{\partial F_{ij}}$$

It is clear that $\frac{\partial G_{mn}}{\partial F_{ij}}$ is non-zero only when F_{ij} shows up in G_{mn} .

If $m = i$ and $k = j$, $G_{mn} = F_{ij} F_{nj}$ and $\frac{\partial G_{mn}}{\partial F_{ij}} = F_{nj}$, so we have

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial F_{ij}} += 2 \sum_n (G_{in} - A_{in}) F_{nj}$$

where $+=$ means that we add the right side of the equation to the left side (assuming the left side was initialized to zero initially).

In matrix form, we have

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial F} += 2(G - A)F$$

If $n = i$ and $k = j$, $G_{mn} = F_{mj} F_{ij}$ and $\frac{\partial G_{mn}}{\partial F_{ij}} = F_{mj}$, so we have

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial F_{ij}} += 2 \sum_m (G_{mi} - A_{mi}) F_{mj}$$

Listing 13: Code for updateGradInput of the TV loss module

```
-- TV loss backward pass inspired by kaishengtai/neuralart
function TVLoss:updateGradInput(input, gradOutput)
    self.gradInput:resizeAs(input):zero()
    local C, H, W = input:size(1), input:size(2), input:size(3)
    self.x_diff:resize(3, H - 1, W - 1)
    self.y_diff:resize(3, H - 1, W - 1)
    self.x_diff:copy(input[{{}}, {1, -2}, {1, -2}])
    self.x_diff:add(-1, input[{{}}, {1, -2}, {2, -1}])
    self.y_diff:copy(input[{{}}, {1, -2}, {1, -2}])
    self.y_diff:add(-1, input[{{}}, {2, -1}, {1, -2}])
    self.gradInput[{{}}, {1, -2}, {1, -2}]:add(self.x_diff):add(self.y_diff)
    self.gradInput[{{}}, {1, -2}, {2, -1}]:add(-1, self.x_diff)
    self.gradInput[{{}}, {2, -1}, {1, -2}]:add(-1, self.y_diff)
    self.gradInput:mul(self.strength)
    self.gradInput:add(gradOutput)
    return self.gradInput
end
```

In matrix form, we have

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial F} += 2(G - A)^T F$$

So, we finally have

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial F} = 2(G - A)F + 2(G - A)^T F$$

Since

$$E = \sum_{m,n} (G_{mn} - A_{mn})^2$$

we have

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial G_{ij}} = 2(G_{ij} - A_{ij})$$

or in matrix form

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial G} = 2(G - A)$$

So, we can write

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial F} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial G} F + \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial G}\right)^T F$$

which is exactly what the updateGradInput method of the Gram matrix module (listing 12) computes as `self.gradInput`.

3.2.3 TVLoss:updateGradInput

The code for the updateGradInput method of the TV loss module is shown in listing 13.

Because the TV loss module (layer) is the first layer of the neural network, `input` in listing 13 is the generated image defined by $x_{i,j}$ for each rgb channel. There is no back propagation here as we are at the end of the line going backwards. `input[{{}}, {1, -2}, {1, -2}]` is a sub-tensor of `input`, the (rgb) generated image. To understand what the sub-tensor looks like, you have to look at the file `tensor.md` in the github torch repository, in particular, this part:

```
[Tensor] sub(dim1s, dim1e ... [, dim4s [, dim4e]])
```

This method is equivalent to do a series of narrow up to the first 4 dimensions. It returns a new Tensor which is a sub-tensor going from index `dimis` to `dimie` in the `i`-th dimension. Negative values are interpreted index starting from the end: `-1` is the last index, `-2` is the index before the last index, ...

Going back to listing 13, `input[{{}}, {1, -2}, {1, -2}]` is `input` without the image last row and last column. Its size is `(3, H-1, W-1)`. Similarly, `input[{{}}, {1, -2}, {2, -1}]` is `input` without the image last row and first column. It can be seen as `input` shifted right. Its size is `(3, H-1, W-1)`.

```
self.x_diff:copy(input[{{}}, {1, -2}, {1, -2}])
self.x_diff:add(-1, input[{{}}, {1, -2}, {2, -1}])
```

computes the gradient in the x direction $x_diff = x_{i,j} - x_{i,j+1}$. The gradient in the y direction $y_diff = x_{i,j} - x_{i+1,j}$ is computed in a similar manner.

Let us compute the derivative of the TV loss with respect to $x_{i,j}$ and see if we can make it match what `TVLoss:updateGradInput` in listing 13 does.

The TV loss is computed as (see [4] using $\beta = 2$)

$$E = \sum_{m,n} ((x_{m,n+1} - x_{m,n})^2 + (x_{m+1,n} - x_{m,n})^2)$$

The derivative of the term inside the sum loss with respect to $x_{i,j}$ is non-zero when $m = i, n = j$, so we have

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial x_{i,j}} += -2(x_{i,j+1} - x_{i,j}) - 2(x_{i+1,j} - x_{i,j})$$

where the notation `+=` means adding the right side to the left side (previously initialized to zero).

The derivative of the term inside the sum loss with respect to $x_{i,j}$ is also non-zero when $m = i, n + 1 = j$, so we have

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial x_{i,j}} += 2(x_{i,j} - x_{i,j-1})$$

The derivative of the term inside the sum loss with respect to $x_{i,j}$ is also non-zero when $m + 1 = i, n = j$, so we have

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial x_{i,j}} += 2(x_{i,j} - x_{i-1,j})$$

Now, we just have to make sure that `self.gradInput` computed in `TVLoss:updateGradInput` in listing 13 is equal to the $\frac{\partial E}{\partial x_{i,j}}$ we just derived.

Going back to listing 13,

```
self.gradInput[{{}}, {1, -2}, {1, -2}]:add(self.x_diff):add(self.y_diff)
```

adds $+(x_{i,j} - x_{i,j+1}) + (x_{i,j} - x_{i+1,j})$ to `self.gradInput`.

In the following line of code

```
self.gradInput[{{}}, {1, -2}, {2, -1}]:add(-1, self.x_diff)
```

`{2, -1}` shifts `self.gradInput` right, meaning, (i, j) becomes $(i, j - 1)$. So, it adds $-(x_{i,j-1} - x_{i,j})$ to `self.gradInput`.

In the following line of code

```
self.gradInput[{{}}, {2, -1}, {1, -2}]:add(-1, self.y_diff)
```

`{2, -1}` shifts `self.gradInput` down, meaning, (i, j) becomes $(i - 1, j)$. So, it adds $-(x_{i-1,j} - x_{i,j})$ to `self.gradInput`.

It is now clear that `self.gradInput` as computed in the code is equal (within a constant factor) to the $\frac{\partial E}{\partial x_{i,j}}$ we derived.

References

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